

MONOTONIC AND CYCLIC FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF HIGH PERFORMANCE CERAMIC FIBERS

N. Chawla¹, M. Kerr¹, and K.K. Chawla²

¹Department of Chemical and Materials Engineering
Arizona State University
P.O. Box 876006
Tempe, AZ 85287-6006

²Department of Materials Science & Engineering
University of Alabama at Birmingham
Birmingham, AL 35294

ABSTRACT

Monotonic and cyclic fatigue behavior of single fibers or fiber fabrics are of significant interest, since fiber assemblies or fiber reinforced composite materials in structural applications are often subjected to cyclic loading. Studying the cyclic fatigue behavior of fibers is particularly difficult because of their small diameter (~10 μm) and high aspect ratio. In this paper, we report results of monotonic tension and tension – tension fatigue behavior of two sol-gel derived ceramic fibers, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2\text{-B}_2\text{O}_3$ (Nextel 312) and Al_2O_3 (Nextel 610). Nextel 312 exhibited a great deal of variability in tensile strength, reflected by a Weibull modulus of 4.6, versus Nextel 610, which had a Weibull modulus of 10.5. Our experiments showed clearly that cyclic loading was more damaging than static loading and, thus, resulted in a lower cyclic fatigue life compared to static loading. The fracture behavior under fatigue loading was distinctly different from that under monotonic loading. It is believed that processing-induced flaws acted as crack initiation sites, and that the cyclic loading induced subcritical cracking, followed by coalescence of cracks immediately prior to failure.

KEYWORDS: Fiber, cyclic fatigue, static fatigue, and crack growth.

INTRODUCTION

High performance continuous fibers are being used in several structural applications, in the form of fabric, rope, or as reinforcement in a composite [1]. Whether in the form of a rope or as reinforcement in a composite, high performance fibers undergo monotonic and/or cyclic deformation. The mechanical behavior of fiber-reinforced composites is inherently dependent on the constitutive properties of the fiber, matrix, and fiber/matrix interface [2]. In particular, the toughness and damage tolerance of brittle matrix composites is controlled by a relatively weak fiber/matrix interface [3, 4]. This weak interface, usually achieved by the incorporation of a fiber coating, promotes energy-absorbing mechanisms such as crack deflection and fiber pullout. Under cyclic loading conditions, however, gradual wear of the fiber coating makes the fiber surface susceptible to stress concentrations, which eventually lead to fiber fracture and composite failure [5-7]. Thus, cumulative fatigue damage in composite materials has been typically attributed to cumulative damage to the matrix or at the fiber/matrix interface. The possibility of cyclic damage in the fiber itself and its effect on composite fatigue behavior has not really been acknowledged [3-7]. Thus, a very important aspect of the fatigue behavior of composites, which has not been studied in detail, is the inherent response of ceramic fiber reinforcement to cyclic loading. In order to obtain a better understanding of the fatigue behavior of various composites, it is of great interest to study the behavior of reinforcement fibers subjected to cyclic fatigue conditions.

Relatively few studies have been conducted on the cyclic fatigue behavior of high performance fibers [8-12]. Most of these studies have examined the stress versus cycles (S-N) behavior of the fibers. Bunsell and Somer [8] examined the fatigue behavior of carbon fibers and reported no significant change in tensile strength after cyclic loading. In fact, they observed a slight increase in fiber modulus with increasing cycles, which was attributed to increasing orientation of the fibrils in the turbostratic structure of graphite fibers. Minoshima et al. [9] studied the cyclic behavior of aramid fibers (Kevlar), and indicated that while inelastic deformation took place due to fatigue, the stress versus cycles behavior was inherently dominated by nodular flaws at the surface of the fibers. Other studies, on the cyclic deformation behavior of natural (polymeric) fibers indicate a cyclic fatigue effect, with fracture taking place by microvoid nucleation and coalescence [12]. In glass fibers, static fatigue plays a role in time-dependent failure, but this is attributed mainly to environmental effects such as moisture absorption [13, 14]. In this paper we examined the monotonic and fatigue behavior of two high performance ceramic fibers; an $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2\text{-B}_2\text{O}_3$ fiber (Nextel 312¹) containing a significant amount of intergranular glassy phase, and a single phase $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ fiber (Nextel 610) with a negligible amount of glassy phase. This comparison is of particular interest because amorphous phases have been shown to contribute to environmental degradation mechanisms such as stress corrosion cracking [15]. A sophisticated microforce testing system was used to conduct fatigue testing on the single fibers, and to determine whether high performance ceramic fibers were susceptible to cyclic damage. The hypothesis of this work is that ceramic fibers indeed undergo cyclic deformation and have lower life at a given cyclic stress than under static loading.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The fiber designation, composition, and microstructural characteristics are summarized in Table I. The fibers were made by 3M corporation using a sol-gel process. Several constituents are added to control the microstructure of the fiber. In Nextel 610, for example, Fe_2O_3 nanosized particles are added to “seed” or nucleate the Al_2O_3 crystals to produce a fine grain size in the fiber [16]. Seeding also decreases the transformation temperature of $\eta\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ to $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$. SiO_2 is also added to reduce the final grain size of the fiber.

Table I. Physical and Chemical Properties of Nextel Fibers

Fiber	Composition	Diameter (μm)	Density (g/cm^3)	Microstructure
Nextel 312	62% Al_2O_3 , 24% SiO_2 , and 14% B_2O_3	10-12	2.7	9 $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-2B}_2\text{O}_3$ grains ($\sim 0.1 \mu\text{m}$) and globular SiO_2 (20 nm)
Nextel 610	99% Al_2O_3 , 0.2-0.3% SiO_2 , 0.4-0.7% Fe_2O_3	10-12	3.75	Single phase $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ grains ($\sim 0.1 \mu\text{m}$)

Fibers were cut from a fiber spool and the organic sizing on the fiber surface was burned out at 725°C for 5 minutes in air prior to testing. A paper frame technique was used to conduct fiber testing, per the ASTM standard for filament testing [17], and proper alignment of the fibers was ensured using an optical microscope. A gage length of 20 mm was used for all tensile and fatigue testing. A microforce testing system was used to conduct tensile and fatigue testing of the ceramic fibers. The load resolution achieved with this system was on the order of 0.001 N and displacement on the order of $1 \mu\text{m}$ were achieved with this system. Tensile testing was conducted in displacement control at a strain rate of $10^{-3}/\text{s}$. Fatigue testing was conducted in stress control, tension-tension with $R = 0.2$ ($\sigma_{\text{min}}/\sigma_{\text{max}}$), at a frequency of 2 Hz. The compliance of the loading and gripping system was quantified by obtaining the force versus displacement

¹ Nextel is a trademark of 3M Corporation.

behavior of the fiber at various gage lengths [1, 17]. The cross-head displacement during fiber testing, δ_t , can be expressed by:

$$\frac{\delta_t}{F} = \left[\frac{1}{EA} \right] \ell + c \quad [1]$$

where c is the machine compliance, F is the applied force, E is the Young's modulus of the fiber, and A is the cross-sectional area of the fiber. Thus, a plot of δ_t/F versus gage length, ℓ , will yield a straight line of slope $1/(EA)$ and intercept c , the compliance of the load train. An average fiber was used to calculate the cross-section area and stress. Recently, Lara-Curzio and Russ [18] have shown that assuming a constant cross-section for all fibers may introduce a significant error in Weibull modulus, particularly when the variability in fiber diameter is quite high. Wilson and Visser [19] made measurements of the fiber diameter for Nextel 610 and determined that the coefficient of variance in fiber diameter was approximately 1.8%. Using the model of Lara-Curzio and Russ [18], Wilson and Visser [19] predicted a reduction in Weibull modulus of only 5%. Thus, since the variability in fiber diameters is quite small, using average fiber diameter in computing Weibull modulus appears to be a reasonable assumption for the fibers studied here. Tensile and fatigue fracture surfaces were examined in a scanning electron microscope (SEM). In order to capture the fractured fiber, petroleum jelly was used to coat the fiber and absorb the strain energy dissipated upon fracture. Other researchers have used similar procedures with no noticeable adverse effects on fiber strength [19].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile behavior

The Young's moduli of the fibers were obtained by measuring force versus displacement at various fiber gage lengths and using the relationship of eq. (1). The measured Young's moduli values of the fibers are shown in Table II. The magnitudes of the Young's moduli of the fibers compare quite well with the values reported in the literature [19-21]. Nextel 610 exhibited a much higher modulus than Nextel 312. This can be explained by the fact that the Young's modulus of Al_2O_3 -based fibers decreases with increasing SiO_2 content [22]. Subtracting the machine compliance yielded the actual stress-strain behavior of the fibers. Measurement of the modulus from the slope of the corrected stress-strain curve yielded similar results to those obtained from the displacement/force versus gage length approach.

Nextel fibers exhibited variability in tensile strength characteristic of ceramic fibers. Weibull statistics were used to rank the relative fiber strength versus probability of failure of the fibers to obtain a measure of the variability in fiber strength [1, 23, 24]. According to the Weibull analysis, the probability of survival of a fiber at a stress, σ , is given by the following relation:

$$P(\sigma) = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \right] \quad [2(a)]$$

where σ is the fiber strength for a given probability of survival, and m is the Weibull modulus. σ_0 is defined as the characteristic strength, which corresponds to $P(\sigma) = \frac{1}{e} = 0.37$. Ranking of the fiber strengths is done by using an estimator given by:

$$P(\sigma)_i = 1 - \frac{i}{N+1} \quad [2(b)]$$

A plot of $\ln \ln \left[\frac{N+1}{N+1-i} \right]$ versus

$\ln(\sigma)$, is linear with slope m , and is shown in Fig. 1. A summary of Young's modulus, Weibull modulus, and tensile strength (50th percentile strength from the Weibull distribution) is shown in Table II. Weibull modulus and Young's modulus compare well with the results of Wilson and Visser [19], as well as the manufacture's data [21], although the tensile strength reported here is somewhat higher. This can be attributed to a smaller gage length used in our study (20 mm vs. 25.4 mm in Wilson and Visser [19]), so a lower volume was tested and, thus, the probability of encountering a strength-limiting flaw also decreased. In comparing Nextel 312 and Nextel 610, the latter fiber exhibited a much lower variability in tensile strength. Variability in fiber strength may be attributed to the variability in fiber flaw size, in the form of porosity or "weld-lines" where two fibers are bonded together during processing [19]. Presumably the smaller average flaw size and narrower distribution of flaws are responsible for the higher strength and higher Weibull modulus observed in Nextel 610, than in Nextel 312.

Figure 1. Weibull distribution of fiber tensile strength. The Weibull modulus, m , of Nextel 610 is much higher than that of Nextel 312, indicating less variability in the tensile strength.

Table II. Tensile Properties of Nextel Fibers

Fiber	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Weibull Modulus, m	Tensile Strength (MPa)
Nextel 312	126	4.6	1667
Nextel 610	388	10.5	3909

The tensile fracture surface of the fibers exhibited three distinct regions. Figure 2 shows typical tensile fracture surfaces of Nextel 312 and Nextel 610. In Nextel 312 fiber a smooth initiation region or fracture mirror is observed at the fiber surface. Surface flaws are more highly stressed than defects in the interior, making a surface flaw a more likely site for crack initiation [25]. Small diameter fibers have a relatively large surface-to-volume ratio, which makes surface flaws on fibers more critical in controlling fiber strength. The crack nucleation site is followed by a transition region or "mist," and the rapid crack propagation region or "hackle." The fracture behavior illustrated here is quite characteristic of brittle ceramic or glass fibers [26, 27]. In Nextel 610 fiber the mist region is not as clear in this fiber and the hackle part of the fracture surface is quite rough, presumably due to the relatively larger grain size of Nextel 610 fiber ($\sim 0.1 \mu\text{m}$), versus that of Nextel 312 (nanocrystalline or amorphous structure).

Cyclic Fatigue Behavior

Cyclic loading caused failure of the fibers at stresses well below the mean (50th percentile of the Weibull distribution) tensile strength of the fibers. While there was a significant amount of variability in fatigue life (also attributable to flaw size distribution), both fibers exhibited a typical stress versus cycles

Figure 2. Fiber fracture surface after tensile loading of: (a) Nextel 312 and (b) Nextel 610, showing mirror-mist-hackle fracture morphology. Nodules on the fiber surface are a result of grease used to dissipate fracture energy and retrieve fibers for fractographic analysis.

behavior, showing higher life at lower cyclic stresses, Figs 3(a) and 3(b). It is interesting to note that the decrease in fatigue strength, relative to tensile strength, is much higher for Nextel 610 than for Nextel 312, although the variability in fatigue life is lower for Nextel 610. The lower variability can be attributed to higher Weibull modulus of Nextel 610. Minor variability in the data may be due to the calculation of stress by using an average diameter.

In order to conclusively demonstrate that cyclic damage was indeed responsible for the observed stress versus cycles behavior, a comparison of cyclic to static behavior of the fibers was conducted. Such a comparison between static and cyclic fatigue lives is necessary because if fiber strength is controlled by time at the applied stress, then the cumulative or “effective” time to failure at the maximum stress under static or cyclic loading should be similar. The static fatigue stress, σ_s , can be related to the time-to-failure, t_s , by the static fatigue exponent, n :

$$t_s = K(\sigma_{\max})^n \quad [3]$$

The analysis of static fatigue data, shown in Figs. 3(c) and 3(d), indicated n values for Nextel 312 and Nextel 610 of 73 and 55, respectively. These values compare well with n values for bulk Al_2O_3 , which can range between 44-78 [28, 29]. comparison of cyclic and static fatigue lives is complicated by the fact that under cyclic loading less time is spent at maximum stress per unit time. Thus, in order to adequately compare the time to failure under static fatigue, t_s , and cyclic fatigue, an effective time to failure under cyclic fatigue, t_c , must be computed. Evans and Fuller [30] proposed that the ratio of t_c and t_s can be written in terms of the cyclic waveform (sinusoidal, trapezoidal, square, etc.) as a function of time. Thus, for a sinusoidal waveform:

$$\frac{t_c}{t_s} = \left\{ \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda \left[\frac{\sigma(t)}{\sigma_s} \right]^n dt \right\}^{-1} \quad [4(a)]$$

where σ_s is the static stress, λ is the period of one cycle, n is the static stress exponent, and $\sigma(t)$ is given by:

$$\sigma(t) = \sigma_m + \sigma_a \sin \omega t \quad [4(b)]$$

where σ_m is the cyclic mean stress, σ_a is the cyclic stress amplitude, and ω is the angular frequency (also equal to $\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$). The $\frac{t_c}{t_s}$ ratio can be written as:

$$\frac{t_c}{t_s} = \left\{ \frac{1+R}{2} + \frac{1-R}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} [\sin^n \theta] d\theta \right\}^{-1} \quad [4(c)]$$

A comparison of applied stress versus time to failure for static fatigue and cyclic fatigue, for both fibers, is shown in Figures 3(c) and 3(d). The predicted cyclic fatigue life computed from the static fatigue life, using the analysis above, is also shown. Note that because of the lower time at maximum stress, the predicted life under cyclic fatigue is longer than that under static fatigue. The actual cyclic fatigue lives, however, are clearly lower than the predicted cyclic fatigue lives. This was particularly true at lower stresses, where the life of the fibers was significantly diminished during cyclic loading. At higher stresses the cyclic and static curves converged, since cyclic damage was not as pronounced and static loading dominated in this regime.

The comparison of actual to predicted cyclic fatigue lives (from static fatigue data) clearly shows that cyclic damage is indeed taking place in the fibers. Fractographic analysis of the fracture surfaces after fatigue was conducted to elucidate the fatigue damage mechanisms, and contrast these to those observed under tensile loading. The cyclic fatigue fracture surfaces of the Nextel 312 fibers were quite different than those observed after tensile loading, Fig. 4(a). Figure 4(a) shows crack initiation at the fiber surface, followed by what appears to be a stable crack, due to cyclic loading, that stemmed from the crack initiating defect. The fast-fracture region of the fiber is also rougher in character than that observed in tension, Fig. 2, with more evidence of damage associated with fatigue microcracks. Figure 4(b) shows a fatigue fracture surface of Nextel 610. Crack initiation in this particular fiber appears to have started at an internal flaw. As observed for the tensile fracture surface of Nextel 610, the 0.1 μm -size grains of the fiber give it a rougher appearance than the nanometer-sized grains of Nextel 312. Thus, qualitative comparisons of the fracture surface roughness, as a means to differentiate between monotonic and cyclic loading are more difficult in Nextel 610. From the fractographic analysis it is possible to conclude that crack initiation in the fibers takes place at preexisting flaws in the material. Thus, the size and distribution of flaws will affect the onset of crack initiation during cyclic loading. We believe that during cyclic fatigue of the fibers, fibers with large flaws failed immediately upon loading in the first cycles, while fibers with smaller flaws had much longer fatigue lives. These smaller flaws likely served as crack initiating defects for subcritical crack growth, which propagated until a critical crack size was formed leading to unstable fracture. The same behavior was observed in cyclic fatigue of monolithic yttria-stabilized zirconia [31]. Thus, our data indicate that cyclic damage has a significant role in nucleating subcritical damage at fatigue strength-limiting flaws. Static fatigue life on the other hand, similar to monotonic tensile loading, appeared to be controlled by critical flaw size, above which instantaneous failure took place, and below which, the fiber did not fail. A similar observation has been made by Hulm and Evans [31] in their study of yttria-stabilized zirconia.

We can gain a better understanding of cyclic damage in the fibers by examining the work on cyclic fatigue of bulk ceramics. Several mechanisms have been proposed for fatigue crack growth in monolithic ceramics, and these have been summarized by Horibe [14]. Cyclic crack growth in ceramics is known to occur predominantly in an intergranular fashion. One mechanism for the intergranular crack growth is dependent on frictional wear mechanisms between grains [32-35]. "Grain bridging" contributes to crack growth resistance, but continued cycling results in debonding between the grains. The contribution from

Figure 3. Cyclic fatigue behavior of: (a) Nextel 312 and (b) Nextel 610. Comparison of cyclic fatigue, static fatigue, and predicted cyclic fatigue life (integrated from static fatigue life) for: (a) Nextel 312 and (b) Nextel 610. The experimental cyclic fatigue life is significantly lower than the predicted cyclic fatigue life, indicating a true cyclic fatigue effect.

Figure 4. Fiber fracture surface after fatigue loading of: (a) Nextel 312 and (b) Nextel 610. Note the distinct fatigue crack initiation sites in both fibers.

grain boundary bridging is very small at very small grains sizes, such as those in the fibers tested here [34]. Crack growth may also be affected by residual glassy phase between grains. Ewart and Suresh [32] showed that pure Al_2O_3 with very little glassy phase did not exhibit subcritical crack growth. Al_2O_3 with some amount of glass phase, however, did exhibit stable crack growth. The Nextel 312 fiber has a substantial amount of glassy phase between grains, while Nextel 610 has a negligible amount of glassy phase. Both fibers were susceptible to cyclic fatigue, so that the presence of a glassy phase does not appear to be a necessary condition for cyclic crack propagation. This is supported by the work of Horibe and Hirahara [36] on reaction bonded silicon nitride, a polycrystalline material with no grain boundary glassy phase between the grains, where cyclic crack propagation took place in intergranular fashion.

Another mechanism for cyclic crack growth in monolithic ceramics, such as Si_3N_4 , involves crack deflection and branching between grains. The crack propagates between the grains and may encounter a grain that arrests the crack until a sufficient driving force is available to grow the crack. Cyclic crack growth in the ceramic fibers studied here is mostly likely occurring by this mechanism. It is envisioned that the cracks initiate at pores or defects at surface or in the interior of the fiber. Because of the extremely fine grain size, the cracks must branch and deflect through the grain boundaries. The fracture surfaces of the fibers after fatigue support this hypothesis. The much rougher fracture surface observed after fatigue, compared to monotonic tensile loading, indicates several nucleation sites for subcritical crack growth and coalescence of these cracks appears to have taken place prior to fatigue fracture. When a large fatigue crack is formed at the surface and propagates through the fiber, interlinking between the dominant fatigue crack and the smaller fatigue cracks within the volume of the fiber may take place. This interlinking may result in a fracture surface that is quite torturous. The crack growth may be accentuated by the accumulation of debris and localized wear between the crack faces, which has been shown to decrease the resistance to cyclic crack growth [36]. The debris may also cause wedging and localized mismatch between crack faces, which may result in roughness-induced closure during fatigue [32, 37]. It should be noted that stress corrosion cracking (SCC) can be accelerated during cyclic loading of ceramics due to moisture, but cyclic crack growth has also been observed in inert or vacuum environments [15]. Since both cyclic and static tests of the fibers were conducted in the same environment (laboratory air), and cyclic loading was clearly more detrimental to fiber life, the effect of cyclic loading is over and above any environmental effect that may be present. Thus, a mechanical component of degradation is certainly present, and the premature failure of ceramics under cyclic loads cannot be explained by chemical interactions at the crack tip alone.

Finally, we wish to emphasize the importance and implications of the results presented here on the fatigue behavior of composites. It is generally accepted that matrix cracking followed by interface wear during cyclic loading are the predominant fatigue damage mechanisms in ceramic matrix composites [2, 5-7]. The results described here indicate that fiber fatigue likely plays a significant role during fatigue damage and cyclic failure of the composite. Subsequent work should focus on incorporating fiber fatigue characteristics toward a more comprehensive understanding and for modeling of cyclic fatigue damage in ceramic matrix composites.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be made regarding the tensile and cyclic fatigue behavior of the two high performance ceramic fibers examined in this study:

- The fibers exhibited significant variability in tensile strength. Nextel 312 fibers and Nextel 610 fibers had Weibull moduli of 4.6 and 10.5, respectively. The variability can be attributed to processing-induced flaws and the probabilistic nature of failure because of defect distribution on the surface and interior of the fiber.
- The experimental observations on cyclic fatigue behavior indicated that cyclic loading induced significant damage and decrease in fatigue life of the fiber. This was clearly demonstrated by the significant decrease in life under cyclic loading vis-a-vis predicted cyclic life (based on time at maximum stress, obtained from static fatigue data).
- It is believed that fatigue damage initiated at pores or defects in the fiber. Fatigue crack growth likely took place by crack arrest and branching mechanisms. This is supported by fractographic analysis of fatigued fibers which indicated a significantly torturous fracture surface under cyclic loading, compared to monotonic loading. This can be attributed to subcritical damage, in the form of microcracks formed during the cyclic process, which are linked in the final stages of fatigue.
- Design of fiber reinforced composites or other applications where high performance fibers are incorporated must take into consideration the cyclic fatigue behavior of the fibers.

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